

Engineering multi-phase metal halide perovskites thin films for stable and efficient solar cells

*Min Kim, Jetsabel M. F. Tapia, Mirko Prato, Annamaria Petrozza**

Dr. Min Kim¹, Jetsabel M. F. Tapia^{1,2}, Dr. Annamaria Petrozza¹

¹Center for Nano Science and Technology@Polimi, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, via Giovanni Pascoli 70/3, 20133 Milan, Italy

²Dipartimento di Fisica, Politecnico di Milano, Piazza L. Da Vinci, 32, 20133 Milan, Italy

Email: annamaria.petrozza@iit.it

Dr. Mirko Prato

Material Characterization Facility, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, via Morego 30, 16163 Genova, Italy

Keywords: metal halide perovskite, solar cells, mixed-dimension, bulky cations, stability

The intrinsic instability of lead halide perovskite materials in ambient atmosphere is one of the most critical issues that impede perovskite solar cell commercialization. To overcome it, the use of bulky organic spacers emerged as promising candidates for stable photovoltaics. The resulting perovskite thin films present complex morphologies, difficult to predict, which will directly affect the device efficiency. Here, by combining in-depth morphological and spectroscopic characterization, we show that both the ionic size and relative concentration of the organic cation drive the integration of bulky organic cations into the crystal unit cell and the thin film, inducing different perovskite phases and different vertical distribution, then causing a significant change in the final morphology. Based on such studies we propose a fine-engineered multi-phases perovskite by employing two different large cations, namely ethyl ammonium and butyl ammonium. **The first one takes part to the 3D perovskite phase formation, the second one works as surface modifier by forming a passivating layer on top of the thin film.** Together they lead to improved photovoltaic

performance and device stability when tested in air under continuous illumination. Our findings propose a general approach to achieve reliability of perovskite-based optoelectronic devices.

1. Introduction

In the past years, organic-inorganic lead halide perovskites have attracted immense interest due to their excellent optoelectronic properties such as strong light absorption, long charge carrier diffusion length, and unique defect tolerance property.^[1-4] More importantly, the power conversion efficiency (PCE) of perovskite solar cells (PSCs) has skyrocketed to a certified PCE of 24.2%.^[5-7] The widely used perovskite materials form $APbX_3$ structure with $A = CH_3NH_3^+$ (methylammonium, MA) and/or $CH_3(NH_2)_2^+$ (formamidinium, FA) and/or cesium (Cs) and $X = Cl^-, Br^-$ or I^- , which crystallizes in a three-dimensional (3D) network.^[7-8] In spite of high PCEs, the long-term device stability of PSCs remains as one of the crucial issues to be overcome for the large-scale commercialization of PSCs.^[9] To solve the stability issue, the introduction of functional cations within perovskite structures has been proposed.

Recently, two-dimensional (2D) halide perovskites have been demonstrated as interesting materials as light absorbers for solar cells and as light emitters for light-emitting diodes because of their wider structural diversity.^[10-11] 2D perovskites can be conceptually obtained by slicing a generic ABX_3 three-dimensional (3D) perovskite network across the inorganic planes, spaced by large organic cations, typically protonated primary amines with an extended linear organic portion.^[12] This results in layered structures with the general formula $R_2(A)_{n-1}B_nX_{3n+1}$, where R is the additional large cation and n represents the number of inorganic slabs spaced by the large organic cations. Good stability has been demonstrated for devices utilizing 2D perovskites^[13-14] as

the only active material, however, they generally deliver poor performance because of their inferior carrier mobility and higher detrimental recombination rates.^[11, 15-16]

In this regard, multidimensional perovskite, which has 2D polymorphs together with 3D perovskites, were brought into perovskite devices, and improved device performances and stability of 2D/3D perovskite have been reported both for solar cells and LEDs.^[11, 17] By blending 2D-forming bulky cations with a 3D perovskite-forming solution 2D/3D heterostructures can be formed at the grain boundaries or at thin film interfaces.^[17-19] For sure, beginning from all the precursors in the same solution, the perovskite conversion process can become more complex because 3D perovskite and 2D perovskite would go through a discrete perovskite conversion process due to their difference in solubility and crystallization property, resulting in non-homogeneous morphology.^[20] In photovoltaic (PV) devices, bulky organic cation mixed into 3D perovskite can add higher complexity for reliable morphology control, which has led to broad statistics of PCE for various 2D/3D mixed perovskite solar cells in the previous literatures, ranging from 8 to 20%.^[16, 21-24] Therefore, the effect of the chemical structure of 2D-forming large cation on the construction of 2D/3D perovskite morphology should be investigated thoroughly.

In this work, we investigate how bulky organic cations, which have an ammonium group and different alkyl lengths, incorporate in multi-dimensional perovskite phase and affect perovskite solar cells in terms of PV properties and device stability. In particular, we compare ethyl ammonium (EA) and butyl ammonium (BA) ions. The BA cation has been used to produce 2D/3D perovskite structures, but there has been a broad statistic of PCEs depending on the chemical composition and processing methods of the thin films.^[24-28] The EA cation, of smaller size, presents the same functional groups. It has been reported as surface passivation molecule and directly within multication 3D perovskites.^[29-30] Nevertheless, the conditions which determine

how this molecule should be used need to be studied thoroughly yet. We focus on these two cations to investigate how they will be integrated within the perovskite thin film in terms of structural and morphological properties and then how this affects the optoelectronic properties and stability upon stimuli of the thin film and the relative solar cells. We show how fine-engineering multi-phases perovskite devices which achieve both high PCE and improved device stability during the device operation under 1 sun illuminations.

2. Results and discussion

As a control system, we used formamidinium (FA) and cesium (Cs) as A-site cations to form the 3D perovskite phase. The FACs perovskite, with a mole ratio of FA:Cs = 0.85:0.15, has been reported to display solar cells with an average PCE around 17%.^[8] Cations larger than FA and Cs, which are not able to fit within the A site of the $APbX_3$ 3D structure, will act as a spacer between $[Pb_nX_{3n}]$ nanoplatelets. To attain a selection criterion of suitable bulky spacers for high-performance solar cells, we started comparing four different ammoniums: ethyl ammonium (EA), butyl ammonium (BA), phenylethyl ammonium (PEA), and 5-ammonium valeric acid (5AVA) as an increasing order of cation size (**Fig. 1a**). The ionic sizes of all the four cations are too large to fit in the tolerance factor below 1, thus, in principle, they form 2D or 1D perovskite structure when they occupy the A site (**Fig. 1b**).^[29, 31-33] We added these large cations into 3D-forming perovskite solution, composed of FA and Cs ($FA_{0.85}Cs_{0.15}PbX_3$ with $X = I_{0.9}Br_{0.1}$), and then we grew the polycrystalline thin film by using a conventional solvent-quench method. The perovskite films were sandwiched between $SnO_2/PCBM$ and spiro-OMeTAD for standard single-junction device configuration. First, we measured the J-V characteristics of PV devices made with a 10-% mole composition of bulky cation and FACs cations (**Fig. 1c**). The J-V curves show that only perovskite

processed with EA shows enhanced PCE while the other three, BA, PEA, and 5AVA, exhibit lower PV performances. Based on these results, we have focused the rest of our investigation on a systematic comparison between EA and BA, which provide a simplified case study.

We started investigating how changing the mole fraction of EA-mixed and BA-mixed perovskite could affect the PV performance. We incorporated the bulky cation into $\text{FA}_{0.85}\text{CS}_{0.15}\text{Pb}(\text{I}_{0.9}\text{Br}_{0.1})_3$ perovskite precursor, ensuring the desired stoichiometry in the resultant films. **Figure 2a** shows the average PV parameters obtained from 24 identical devices for each system. In the case of the EA-FACs devices, the PV statistics show an obviously increasing trend for PCE from $x = 3$ to 10%. Then, when the EA composition reaches 20% or above, the device shows a decrease in PCE. This trend reflects all the PV parameters such as open circuit voltage (V_{oc}), short circuit current density (J_{sc}), and fill factors (FF). On the other hand, the BA-FACs devices show a continuous decrease in all of the figures of merit as increasing the BA composition. Thus we have chosen 10% concentration of the cation to further advance our investigations.

The control FACs perovskite exhibits a V_{oc} of 1.08 V, a J_{sc} of 20.5 mA cm^{-2} , and a FF of 0.72, yielding an average PCE of 16.2%.^[34] The device employing EA10%-FACs perovskite film achieves higher V_{oc} of 1.11 V, a J_{sc} of 21.2 mA cm^{-2} , and an FF of 0.76, leading to an improved PCE of 17.9%. However, the BA10%-FACs device exhibits an inferior performance with lower PV parameters: a V_{oc} of 0.94 V, a J_{sc} of 17.6 mA cm^{-2} , and an FF of 0.55. Figure 2d shows the corresponding EQE spectra for the best PV device for each cation. **Table 1** summarizes the corresponding PV parameters of the best cells and their averaged values. The EQE of the EA-FACs device has a higher average value in the wavelength range from 300 to 800 nm compared to the control and BA-FACs. All of the integrated J_{sc} values from the three devices are well-matched with the values from the J–V results.

The reduced J_{sc} and V_{oc} of BA10%-FACs are closely related to charge recombination processes in the device. First, we measured J_{sc} under different light intensities (I) ranging from 5 to 100 mW cm^{-2} (Fig. 2e). J_{sc} goes $\propto I^\alpha$, where α should be close to 1 if the devices have sufficient electron and hole mobilities and no space charge effects.^[35] The fitted α values are 0.994, 0.998, and 0.964 for the control FACs, the EA-FACs, and BA-FACs, respectively. The BA-FACs device shows a stronger deviation from the unity of slope, which might be related to stronger charge recombination than the control and EA-FACs.

We also measured V_{oc} at different I (Fig. 2f). V_{oc} depends logarithmically on I with a pre-factor, the so-called diode ideality factor n_{id} , which can be determined from a measurement of V_{oc} as a function of I .^[36]

$$V_{oc} = \frac{E_g}{q} - \frac{n_{id}kT}{q} \ln\left(\frac{I_0}{I}\right)$$

with E_g the band gap energy, n_{id} the ideality factor, k the Boltzmann constant, T the temperature, q is the elementary charge, and I_0 is a constant with the same unit as I . The FACs and EA-FACs devices show $n_{id} = 1.62$, which is reasonably in agreement with the reported values ranging from 1.6 to 1.8 in the previous papers.^[36] It is associated to Shockley-Read-Hall recombination processes in the bulk of a mostly intrinsic perovskite film. On the other hand, the BA-FACs device shows n_{id} of 1.44 together with lower V_{oc} values than 1 V. This low n_{id} along with a low V_{oc} might indicate strong surface recombination in PV devices, which has been observed for perovskite solar cells with an energy-level-unmatched electrode or without hole transporting layer.^[36-37] To understand this large difference in PV property between EA-FACs and BA-FACs, the morphology of mixed-phase perovskites is further investigated by UV-Vis absorption, photoluminescence, and X-ray diffraction.

Ultraviolet-visible (UV - vis) absorption and photoluminescence (PL) spectra are measured for the perovskite films with a mixed cation composition of $R_x(\text{FA}_{0.85}\text{Cs}_{0.17})_{1-x}\text{Pb}(\text{I}_{0.9}\text{Br}_{0.1})_3$, shortly $R(\text{mole}\%)$ -FACs ($R = \text{EA}$ or BA). We prepared the mixed cation perovskite films from starting solutions having the bulky cation R and FACs cation at desirable component ratios and also have PbX_2 to be the equivalent molarity to the R -FACs cation for all the solutions. Therefore, the label $\text{EA}_x(\text{FACs})_{1-x}$ indicates that the perovskite film was processed from the starting solutions that have $\text{EA}_x(\text{FACs})_{1-x}\text{I}$ and PbX_2 . The EA-FACs perovskites with 5 and 10% molar ratio of EA show an almost unchanged absorption profile (**Fig. 3a**). When the EA content reaches 20%, the mixed-phase films show multiple slopes in the absorption spectra. The absorption peaks observed at 494, 522, 560, and 600 nm can be attributed to the smaller n components ($n = 1, 2, 3,$ and 4), where n represents the number of inorganic slabs spaced by the large organic cations, suggesting that multiple phase components coexist in the EA-FACs films. On the other hand, the BA-mixed FACs perovskites show a gradual decrease in absorption as increasing the mole fraction of BA and show strongly enhanced background scattering (Fig. 3b). This background scattering suggests a rougher surface profile of BA-FACs perovskite films. The absorption edges of the FACs films are maintained also in the BA-FACs till 50-% mole ratio. Thus, the 3D phase disappears only for 100%-EA (processed from $\text{EAI}:\text{PbI}_2 = 1:1$) and 100%-BA (processed from $\text{BAI}:\text{PbI}_2 = 1:1$) which shows an excitonic absorption peak at ~ 500 nm.

The pristine FACs shows a main PL emission peak at 795 nm (Fig. 3c). The PL emission peaks slightly shift from 795 to 756 nm for the samples with the EA amount increasing from 10% to 50%, which is consistent with the UV-vis absorption results. Importantly, the PL spectra of the films show only one main peak indicating a good transfer of the photoexcitation to the 3D phase with the smaller bandgap. The 100% EA shows a broad PL emission peak at 585 nm with a large

Stokes shift. The large Stokes shift could in part be attributed to the so-called edge states that are characteristic of layered 2D perovskite materials.^[38] On the other hand, the PL spectra of BA-mixed FACs from 10% to 50% mole ratio exhibit a main PL emission peak at 795 nm with well-defined emission signals from low-dimensional perovskites at 580 nm (corresponding to $n = 2$) and 700 nm ($n = 3$ or higher) (Fig. 3d). The 100% BA shows the characteristic PL peak of low dimension perovskite $n = 1$ (BA_2PbI_4) at 520 nm. These PL peaks at shorter wavelengths are in agreement with values reported in the literature for BA-based low-dimension perovskite arranging into a Ruddlesden - Popper phase.^[39] These multiple PL peaks in 2D/3D perovskite indicate that there is no transfer of the photoexcitation between low dimension and high dimension perovskite.

XRD patterns were measured to understand the arrangement of large cations in the 2D/3D perovskite structure (**Fig. 4**). The control FACs perovskite shows typical diffraction profiles of 3D perovskite phase which has a (110) diffraction peak at 14.05° . The diffraction profiles of the EA5%- and EA10%-FACs perovskite films show similar diffraction peaks to the control FACs perovskite but with a slight shift of the (110) diffraction peak toward smaller angle at 14.0° without low n phase perovskite formation. Considering the ionic size of the EA cation that is slightly larger than FA, we can assume that EA is compatible with a 3D structure, placing in the “quasi-3D” structure. Thus, we suggest that EA amounts as small as 10% can still form a 3D perovskite phase with a slight lattice expansion. Interestingly, the EA5%- and EA10%-FACs films show stronger (110), (220), and (310) diffraction peaks from 3D perovskite phase than the FACs film, which indicates that EA addition of 5 - 10% induces higher crystallinity of perovskite film (Fig. 4c).^{[40-}
^{41]} We also observe that the PbI_2 peak at 12.7° reduces with the EA addition, which indicates that the remnant PbI_2 gets involved in perovskite formation with EA cation.^[42-43] Beyond $x = 0.2$, $\text{EA}_x(\text{FACs})_{1-x}$ starts to show a diffraction peak from the low dimensional phase in the perovskite

film at a peak of 8° (corresponding to $n = 2$). The diffraction scan of the EA50%-FACs shows the $n = 1$ diffraction peak from EA₂PbI₄ phase, located at 11.7° , and a weakened (110) diffraction peak from 3D perovskite phase.^[44] The d-spacing from the $n = 1$ diffraction peak is 11.1 \AA , which corresponds to the (020) plane with a stack of EA spacers. On the other hand, the BA-FACs perovskite shows a $n = 2$ diffraction peak at 4.5° already from the BA composition of 10% (Fig. 4b). Due to the large size of BA cation, it does not incorporate into 3D perovskite phase at all, but it forms a 2D perovskite phase. The $n = 2$ diffraction peak comes from (020) plane, reflection at 4.5° is observed for the BA-FACs film, which corresponds to the (020) crystal plane of the 2D perovskite phase. The BA-FACs films display similar or slightly weaker (110), (220), and (310) diffraction peaks from 3D perovskite phase, compared to the FACs control (Fig. 4d). As increasing BA composition, diffraction peaks from low-dimensional perovskite phase become prominent until 50%. In the case of BA100% perovskite, it exhibits $n = 1$ diffraction peak at 5.8° from BA₂PbI₄ phase.^[45]

To elucidate where the bulky cation locates in the 2D/3D perovskite films, we measured dynamic secondary ion mass spectrometry (DSIMS) and obtained depth profile of ionic species coming from the perovskite film under the Cs⁺ ionic sputtering. The control FACs perovskite film shows a homogeneous distribution of every component including Pb, CN₂ ion, and I ion along with the depth profile (**Fig. 5a**). The EA10%-FACs perovskite also exhibits a similar depth profile except a small bump locating an accumulation of CN₂ at the buried interface (Fig. 5b). Discerning FA (CH₅N₂, MW = 172) and EA (C₂H₈N, MW = 173) cations is difficult since they have similar molecular weights. However, it has been reported by previous works that bulky cations in 2D/3D perovskites are likely to accumulate at the buried interface.^[46-48] XPS measurement shows an identical surface chemical composition of EA-FACs and FACs film (Table S1) which may indicate

that EA falls to the buried interface. In the case of the BA10%-FACs film, the depth profile displays a strong peak of carbon signal at the buried interface with a thickness around 150 nm, which can be definitely differentiated from the CN₂ curve that already shows a substantial decrease at the buried interface (Fig. 5c). This carbon accumulation comes from the BA cation that has three more carbons than FA. Such vertical distribution is also confirmed by the detection of photoluminescence spectra from the top and buried perovskite surface (Fig. S2).

We measured SEM images of the control FACs, EA10%-FACs, and BA10%-FACs perovskites to investigate the perovskite film morphologies. The control FACs shows a quite broad distribution of crystal size ranging from 0.2 to 1 μm, whereas the EA-FACs exhibits larger crystals averagely over 1 μm and smoother surface morphology with reduced surface roughness. The EA-FACs film seems to contain more compactly packed crystals. On the other hand, the BA-FACs shows a much rougher surface morphology than the control and EA-FACs. In particular, the topology of the BA-FACs film shows a wrinkly-textured morphology with a width of 20 μm between wrinkles. This can be explained by a high degree of the volume changes that occur during perovskite conversion processes due to the much larger size of BA cation compared to FA and Cs, resulting in the development of in-plane compressive stress that leads to the observed wrinkling upon releasing energy.^[49] Especially, the BA-based low *n* perovskite phase dominantly forms at the buried interface, strongly affecting the overall film morphology development. Interestingly, this wrinkly morphology also appears in the case of EA50%-FACs, with a similar valley width of 20 μm, which supports that low *n* perovskite formation during rapid crystallization can affect resultant film formation strongly (Fig. S3).

In **Figure 6**, we present a schematic drawing which summarizes the thin film morphology evolution upon doping with large organic cations. Up to 10% load with the EA cation, the molecule

remains disperse within the 3D phase and at the bottom without forming a 2D perovskite phase. Only above 10% of the EA cation concentration 2D crystalline phases start forming. Most importantly, the incorporation of EA induces a smooth, compact, and large-size perovskite crystal formation as confirmed by XRD and SEM measurements. This also results in a lower defect density and enhanced PL emission with respect to the control sample (Fig. S4) and a good thermal stability (Fig S7). Above 20% EA mole fraction, perovskite starts to form $n = 2$ phase layer at the buried interface, and the thin film morphology also shows smaller grains. By introducing a novel molecular descriptor for larger molecular cations, the “globularity factor” (i.e., the discrepancy of the molecular shape and an ideal sphere), it was shown that EA may be a suitable candidate for multi-cation 3D perovskites.^[29, 50] MA/EA perovskite solar cells with very large EA loading were characterized.^[29] However, here it is clear that different cations combinations, i.e. the addition of FA/Cs, can affect the stabilization of single components within the structure and the thin film morphology at different loads. On the other hand, even with a small amount of BA addition, the perovskite thin film shows $n = 2$ phase formation and a much rough surface morphology with small perovskite grains. The inclusion of BA in the 3D perovskite phase induces strong vertical segregation and large volume expansion, which substantially affects 2D/3D film formation. Though the film still shows good emissive and thermal properties (Fig S4 and Fig S7), this segregation will act as a barrier for charge transport and collection to the electrode and induces surface recombination, as shown in Fig 2.

To gain insight into the operational stability of the mixed 2D/3D perovskite solar cells, maximum power point (MPP) of PV device was tracked under 1 sun illumination (UV spectrum included) for 60 h in a way of simulating day and night cycle for 12-h illumination and overnight storages (**Fig. 7a**). We compared the control FACs, EA10%-FACs, and BA10%-FACs devices. This

cycling test monitors not only the device operational stability but also the recovering property in the dark.^[51] The devices were measured in ambient condition at a relative humidity of 40 ~ 70% and a room temperature of 19 ~ 21°C without encapsulations. The MPP of the EA10%-FACs device is stable at 17% without showing any decay over the entire probing period of 60 h. The control FACs and BA10%-FACs devices show a stark contrast to the EA10%-FACs. For the 1st-day stability test, they do not show any decrease in MPPT similar to the EA-FACs device, but on the 2nd day, it exhibits an apparent decay in MPPT by 20%. In addition, on the third day, even though the MPP recovers back of its initial value, it rapidly decays to 40% of the PCE over the 12-h illumination. The BA-FACs device also exhibits a similar trend to the control FACs device. Especially, on the third day of illumination, it obviously shows a decay in PCE during the testing process by 40%. This trend is in agreement with the reported results, which showed a decrease by 40 - 60% in MPPT during tens of hours without encapsulation in an ambient atmosphere.^[17, 19]

Armed with the knowledge developed in this study, we further engineered our PV devices. Because the addition of the bulky cation, BA, in the precursor solution induces a dramatic morphological change, instead we deposited BAI thin film on top of perovskite not to disrupt the morphology, while acting as a surface encapsulation agent on the control FACs perovskite (**Fig 8a**). For comparison we also test thin film with EAI treated surfaces (Fig 8b). The BAI-coated FACs device a slightly higher V_{oc} (1.12 V) compared to the reference without the BAI layer (1.08 V) and the one with BAI mixed within the precursors' solutions (Fig. 8a and Table S2). **Note that by depositing the BAI salt on the FACs and EA-FACs surfaces, even though the samples were not subject to thermal annealing, we found that a 2D phase is formed probably (see Fig S9 and S10) due to a diffusion of the large cation within the first tens of seconds.**^[52-54] In the case of EAI-overcoating, the EAI(top)/FACs perovskite shows a similar J-V curve to the control device without

an improvement in V_{oc} (1.08 V), contrary to the increase in V_{oc} (1.12 V) of the EA-mixed perovskite (Fig. 8b). As an obvious conclusion, we tried to combine this BAI interlayer modification with the high-performing EA-FACs PV device. We fabricated a multi-structured 2D/3D perovskite PV device that has EA10%-FACs in the bulk and BAI thin film between the perovskite and spiro-OMeTAD. The BAI/EA10%-FACs device achieves the highest PCE with the average V_{oc} of 1.14V and the stabilized PCE of 18% with the champion PCE of 18.8% (Fig. 8c and 8d). We believe that our approach to utilize BAI-passivated and EA doped perovskite will provide important insights for the research community to design perovskite materials to achieve stabilized PCEs over long-term operation.

3. Conclusion

We investigated how the integration of bulky cations can affect the structural, optical and morphological properties of FACsPbX₃ perovskite thin films. We have chosen two molecules that represent an ideal model system since they have the same functional groups but different sizes, i.e. ethyl ammonium and butyl ammonium. By following the morphological evolution and the relative consequences on the optoelectronic mechanisms of the solar cells, we have engineered a multi-phase system where the ethyl ammonium is dispersed within the thin film and mainly improves the crystallinity of the perovskite by entering the crystal unit, while the bigger butyl ammonium is used to treat the 3D surface, passivating it. This structure can achieve both improved PCE and improved device operational stability, ~~suggesting that the most effective role of these cations regards the role of passivating agents~~. This study provides a promise for improving the air-stability of perovskite-based optoelectronic devices.

4. Experimental

Materials. All materials were purchased and used as received. PbI_2 , PbBr_2 , and CsI were purchased from Alfa Aesar. Formamidinium iodide (FAI), ethyl ammonium iodide (EAI), and butyl ammonium iodide (BAI) were obtained from Dyesol. *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF), dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Spiro-OMeTAD was purchased from Luminescence Technology.

Perovskite fabrication. FTO-coated glass was etched with zinc powder and 2M aqueous HCl solution for electrode pattern. The ITO substrates were washed with 2% Hellmanex in water, deionized water, iso-propanol, acetone, and iso-propanol sequentially in a sonication bath for ~ 15 min, followed by O_2 plasma cleaning for 10 min. A patterned and cleaned FTO substrate was covered with a ~10 nm thick SnO_2 layer by spin-coating of a diluted SnO_2 nanoparticle solution (Alfa Aesar) and annealed at 180 °C for 1 h. And then, PCBM solution (10 mg·ml⁻¹ in chlorobenzene) was deposited on SnO_2 , followed by annealing at 100 °C for 10 min. The 3D perovskite FA/Cs perovskite was prepared by dissolving different molar quantities of FAI, CsI, PbI_2 , and PbBr_2 , which forms $\text{FA}_{0.85}\text{Cs}_{0.15}\text{Pb}(\text{I}_{0.9}\text{Br}_{0.1})_3$, in DMF and DMSO at a volume ratio of 7:3. For 2D/3D perovskite solutions, stoichiometric precursor solutions were prepared by mixing FACs with EAI and/or BAI to get the molar ratio between $\text{FA}_{0.85}\text{Cs}_{0.15}$ and large cation (EA or BA), gradually changing from 1:0 to 0:1, while keeping the $\text{Pb}(\text{I}_{0.9}\text{Br}_{0.1})_2$ molarity all the same. After stirring for 6 h at room temperature, the perovskite solutions were spin-coated with two steps (the first step at 1000 rpm for 10 s and the second step at 4000 rpm for 30 s). During the second step, 200 μL of anhydrous chlorobenzene was quickly dripped at the 15th s. The thin films were then transferred to a hotplate and annealed at 170 °C for 10 min. The whole synthesis process was conducted in the nitrogen-filled glovebox. For photovoltaic device fabrication, a spiro-MeOTAD

solution was spin-coated on the perovskite layer at 4000 rpm for 30 s. Spiro-MeOTAD solution was prepared by dissolving 73 mg of spiro-MeOTAD in 1 ml chlorobenzene (99.8%; Sigma-Aldrich), to which were added 28.8 ml of 4-tert-butylpyridine (96%, Sigma-Aldrich), and 17.5 ml lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (LiTFSI) solution (520 mg LiTFSI in 1 ml acetonitrile, 99.8%, Sigma-Aldrich). Finally, 75 nm gold was thermally evaporated on top of the device at a pressure of 1×10^{-6} mbar to form the back contact.

Characterization. UV-vis absorption spectra are recorded with a UV-vis Varian Cary 5000. Perovskite films were prepared on bare glass substrates. XRD patterns were recorded with a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer with Bragg–Brentano geometry equipped with a Cu $K\alpha_1$ ($\lambda = 1.544060$ Å) anode, operating at 40 kV and 40 mA. All the diffraction patterns were collected at room temperature, with a step size of 0.021 in symmetric scan reflection mode and an acquisition time of 1 s. Dynamic secondary ion mass spectrometry (DSIMS) measurements were taken performed by using a SIMS system (IMS 6F, CAMECA, France) at the National Center for National Institute for Nanomaterials Technology (Pohang, Korea). The impact energy was 10 keV and Cs^+ ions were used as the primary ions; the analysis area was 30 mm, and the raster size was $250 \mu\text{m} \times 250 \mu\text{m}$, accepting negatively charged secondary ions from the central 20% of the crater area. ^{12}C , $^{12}\text{C}^{14}\text{N}_2$, ^{79}Br , ^{107}Ag , ^{120}Sn , ^{127}I , ^{208}Pb ions were detected. The samples were sufficiently thin and conductive so that no charge compensation was required. SEM images were obtained using a JCM-6010LV, JEOL at 15–20 kV electron beam. For steady-state photoluminescence, excitation light was provided by a CW diode laser (Oxxius laserboxx, wavelength 405 nm). The perovskite films were mounted inside a vacuum chamber (pressure of 10^{-5} mbar), and PL was collected in reflection mode and focused into a fiber-coupled to a spectrometer (Ocean Optics Maya Pro 2000).

Photovoltaic characterization. The current density–voltage (J–V) characteristics were measured with a computer-controlled Keithley 2420 source meter in the air without any device encapsulation. The simulated Air Mass 1.5 Global (AM 1.5G) irradiance was provided with a class AAA Newport solar simulator. The light intensity was calibrated with a silicon reference cell with a spectral mismatch factor of 0.99. The active area of the complete device was determined by an illumination-shadowing mask which is 0.0935 cm^2 . For the J–V measurement, the scan rate was 0.05 V s^{-1} for the slow scan. The forward scan started from 0 V (the short circuit condition) to 1.4 V, while the reverse scan was from 1.4 V to 0 V. Pre-conditional stress was not done for PV measurements. The EQE was measured with a home-built setup. EQE spectra were recorded using the monochromated (Bentham) output from a tungsten halogen lamp calibrated with a Newport UV-818 photodiode. The stability test was performed in an ambient atmosphere (temperature: ~ 24 °C, relative humidity = 40 - 70%) by using Arkeo stability platform (Cicci Research, Italy). Devices were maintained at the maximum power point using a MPP tracking algorithm under 1 SUN illumination, and I–V curves were characterized every 1 h by an electronic system.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

M.K. acknowledges funding from EU Horizon 2020 via a Marie Skłodowska Curie Fellowship (Project No. 797546, FASTEST). The authors thank the National Institute for Nanomaterials Technology (NINT, Korea) for DSIMS measurements and also would like to thank Dr. E. M. Speller for help with PL measurements.

Received: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

Revised: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

Published online: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

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Figure caption

Figure 1. (a) A-site organic cations and their ionic sizes: formamidinium (FA), ethyl ammonium (EA), butyl ammonium (BA), phenylethyl ammonium (PEA), and 5-ammonium valeric acid (5AVA). (b) Tolerance factor of APbI₃ perovskite with various A cations. (c) J-V curves of double-cation-based (FA_{0.85}CS_{0.15}) perovskite photovoltaic devices mixed with bulky organic cations at a mole composition of 10%.

Figure 2. (a, b, c) Photovoltaic parameters determined from the J-V characteristic of the perovskite solar cells prepared with EA_x(FACs)_{1-x} or BA_x(FACs)_{1-x} as a function of mole fraction, x (FACs = FA_{0.85}CS_{0.15}Pb(I_{0.9}Br_{0.1})₃). (d) EQE spectra of the photovoltaic devices. (e, f) J_{sc} and V_{oc} as a function of light intensity.

Figure 3. (a, b) Absorption spectra and (c, d) photoluminescence spectra of the 2D/3D perovskite heterostructures with various compositions. At the excitation wavelength of 405 nm, PL was measured from the glass side. We fixed the component ratio of A-site cation and PbX₂ to be 1:1 for all the solutions. The labels EA_x(FACs)_{1-x} and BA_x(FACs)_{1-x} represent that the perovskite film was processed from the starting solutions that have EA_x(FACs)_{1-x}I and Pb(I_{0.9}Br_{0.1})₂ at equimolar ratio.

Figure 4. (a, b) XRD pattern of the perovskite film with EA and/or BA at various compositions. (c, d) Magnification of the XRD peaks on the variation of the EA and/or BA content.

Figure 5. (a, b, c) Dynamic-SIMS depth profiles of secondary ions: C, CN₂, Pb, I, and Sn ions were detected as a function of etching depth. (d, e) Comparison of the emission spectra of the 2D/3D perovskite film illuminated from the front and glass (back) sides of the film.

Figure 6. Schematic representations of the 2D/3D perovskite starting from various compositions and bulk cations.

Figure 7. Operational stability tests without encapsulation by tracking at their maximum power points (MPPs) under 1-sun illumination by xenon lamp.

Figure 8. J-V curves of (a) the FACs device with BAI layer on top of perovskite (orange) and the BA10%-FACs device (blue) and those of (b) the FACs device with EAI layer on top of perovskite (red) and the EA10%-FACs device (blue). The dotted lines are for forward scans and the solid lines are for reverse scans. (c) J-V curves of the EA10%-FACs device with BAI layer on top of perovskite (green) and the EA10%-FACs device (blue). (d) Statistical PCE and V_{oc} for the PSCs obtained from 24 devices.

Table 1. Photovoltaic parameters obtained from J-V curves under 1 sun illumination

	Scan direction	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (V)	PCE_{avg} (%)	FF	J_{sc} from EQE (mA/cm ²)	PCE_{best} (%)
FACs	forward	20.55	1.08	16.20	0.72	21.08	17.39
	reverse	20.52	1.08	16.26	0.72		
EA _{0.1} (FACs) _{0.9}	forward	21.25	1.11	17.86	0.76	22.22	18.77
	reverse	21.21	1.11	17.95	0.76		
BA _{0.1} (FACs) _{0.9}	forward	17.57	0.94	9.15	0.55	18.58	9.91
	reverse	17.52	0.97	9.12	0.53		

Figure 1. (a) A-site organic cations and their ionic sizes: formamidinium (FA), ethyl ammonium (EA), butyl ammonium (BA), phenylethyl ammonium (PEA), and 5-ammonium valeric acid (5AVA). (b) Tolerance factor of APbI₃ perovskite with various A cations. (c) J-V curves of double-cation-based (FA_{0.85}Cs_{0.15}) perovskite photovoltaic devices mixed with bulky organic cations at a mole composition of 10%.

Figure 2. (a, b, c) Photovoltaic parameters determined from the J–V characteristic of the perovskite solar cells prepared with $EA_x(FACs)_{1-x}$ or $BA_x(FACs)_{1-x}$ as a function of mole fraction, x (FACs = $FA_{0.85}Cs_{0.15}Pb(I_{0.9}Br_{0.1})_3$). (d) EQE spectra of the photovoltaic devices. (e, f) J_{sc} and V_{oc} as a function of light intensity.

Figure 3. (a, b) Absorption spectra and (c, d) photoluminescence spectra of the 2D/3D perovskite heterostructures with various compositions. At the excitation wavelength of 405 nm, PL was measured from the glass side. We fixed the component ratio of A-site cation and PbX_2 to be 1:1 for all the solutions. The labels $\text{EA}_x(\text{FACs})_{1-x}$ and $\text{BA}_x(\text{FACs})_{1-x}$ represent that the perovskite film was processed from the starting solutions that have $\text{EA}_x(\text{FACs})_{1-x}\text{I}$ and $\text{Pb}(\text{I}_{0.9}\text{Br}_{0.1})_2$ at equimolar ratio.

Figure 4. (a, b) XRD pattern of the perovskite film with EA and/or BA at various compositions. (c, d) Magnification of the XRD peaks on the variation of the EA and/or BA content.

Figure 5. (a, b, c) Dynamic-SIMS depth profiles of secondary ions: C, CN₂, Pb, I, and Sn ions were detected as a function of etching depth. (d, e) Comparison of the emission spectra of the 2D/3D perovskite film illuminated from the front and glass (back) sides of the film.

Figure 7. Operational stability tests without encapsulation by tracking at their maximum power points under 1-sun illumination by xenon lamp. RH 40% -70%

Figure 8. J-V curves of (a) the FACs device with BAI layer on top of perovskite (orange) and the BAI10%-FACs device (blue) and those of (b) the FACs device with EAI layer on top of perovskite (red) and the EA10%-FACs device (blue). The dashed lines are for forward scans and the solid lines are for reverse scans. (c) J-V curves of the EA10%-FACs device with BAI layer on top of perovskite (green), the EA10%-FACs device (blue), and the FACs control device (black). (d) Statistical PCE and V_{oc} for the PSCs obtained from 24 devices.

This study pictures the complex morphological evolution of perovskites thin films when organic cation of different size and concentration are blended together and proposes an effective solution with strong technological relevance, which demonstrates a stable perovskite solar cell showing its stable performances for tens of hours at the maximum power point, without encapsulation, at 50% RH.

Keyword metal halide perovskite, solar cells, mixed-dimension, bulky cations, stability

Min Kim, Jetsabel M. F. Tapia, Mirko Prato, Annamaria Petrozza*

Engineering multi-phase metal halide perovskites thin films for stable and efficient solar cells

Supporting Information

Engineering multi-phase metal halide perovskites thin films for stable and efficient solar cells

*Min Kim, Jetsabel M. F. Tapia, Mirko Prato, Annamaria Petrozza**

Dr. Min Kim¹, Jetsabel M. F. Tapia^{1,2}, Dr. Annamaria Petrozza¹

¹Center for Nano Science and Technology@Polimi, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, via Giovanni Pascoli 70/3, 20133 Milan, Italy

²Dipartimento di Fisica, Politecnico di Milano, Piazza L. Da Vinci, 32, 20133 Milan, Italy

Email: annamaria.petrozza@iit.it

Dr. Mirko Prato

Material Characterization Facility, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, via Morego 30, 16163 Genova, Italy

Table S1. Atomic composition obtained from XPS analysis

	Cs (at%)	C (at%)	N (at%)	Pb at%)	I (at%)	Br (at%)
FACs	1.4	33.8	20.3	12.1	29	3.4
EA10%FACs	1.3	34.6	19.9	12	29.2	3

Table S2. Average photovoltaic parameters obtained from J-V curves under 1 sun illumination.

	Scan direction	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (V)	PCE_{avg} (%)	FF
FACs	forward	20.55	1.08	16.20	0.72
	reverse	20.52	1.08	16.26	0.72
EA10%-FACs	forward	21.25	1.11	17.86	0.76
	reverse	21.21	1.11	17.95	0.76
BA10%-FACs	forward	17.57	0.94	9.15	0.55
	reverse	17.52	0.97	9.12	0.53
EAI(top)/FACs	forward	20.16	1.08	16.61	0.74
	reverse	20.15	1.08	16.97	0.76
BAI(top)/FACs	forward	21.55	1.09	17.72	0.76
	reverse	21.50	1.09	17.11	0.74
BAI(top)/ EA10%-FACs	forward	21.66	1.13	19.58	0.80
	reverse	21.61	1.13	18.80	0.77

Figure S1. XRD pattern of the perovskite film with EA and BA at various compositions.

Figure S2. Comparison of the emission spectra of the 2D/3D perovskite film illuminated from the front and glass (back) sides of the film.

To further characterize the phase distribution of the deposited films, the PL spectra were measured under two excitation configurations of the front and back side (glass) with the excitation wavelength (405 nm). For the EA-FACs perovskite, there is no difference in the PL spectra between the front and back excitation, only showing a major emission peak at 795 nm which comes from 3D perovskite phase. Though as increasing the EA molar composition to 50%, the PL spectra maintain its shape as a mono-peak with a blue-shift due to lattice distortion. From the UV-Vis and XRD analysis that EA-FACs has multi-dimensional mixed phase, we explain that the mono-peak PL spectra of EA-FACs are attributed to efficient energy and charge funneling from the low n -phase of EA perovskite to high n -phase. In contrast, the PL spectrum of the BA-FACs perovskite shows three emission peaks at higher energy only under back-excitation, which comes from the perovskite phases ($n = 2, 3$ and 4), with a dominant emission peak at ~ 795 nm ($n \approx \infty$). Under front-excitation, it exhibits only a dominant PL peak of the 3D phase. This PL difference between surface and bottom excitation can be observed through 10% to 50% molar composition of BA.

The difference of the PL spectra between the front and back excitations suggests that in the BA small n perovskite phases are predominantly located at the bottom, whereas the 3D perovskite phases are located on the upper surface of the film.

Figure S3. SEM images of the 2D/3D perovskite films.

Figure S4. a) Relative PLQY of the 2D/3D perovskite thin films without and with EA 10% and/or BA 10% plotted as a function of fluence. b) PL spectra of the 2D/3D perovskite films under the excitation wavelength of 405 nm from CW laser at a fluence of 154 mW·cm⁻².

Figure S4 shows the relative PLQY of thin perovskite films prepared on glass substrates, which is calculated as the integrated PL intensity divided by the excitation intensity, and plotted as a function of fluence, in the range between 15 and 275 mW·cm⁻² (continuous wave (CW) illumination). To exclude the effect of oxygen in the air, the samples were kept and measured in a vacuum (pressure < 10⁻⁵ mbar). The solid lines show the PLQY collected with increasing excitation intensity. The reference FACs shows an increasing trend of PLQYs from low to high excitation intensities. This result originates from the effect of filling trap states with higher carrier densities. The EA10%-FACs and BA10%-FACs perovskite behave differently from the reference. The slopes of relative PLQY as increasing fluence are smaller compared to the control. Furthermore, the PL counts of those films largely increase with respect to that of the reference. These results infer that the large cations, EA and BA, heal defect states in the thin film surface by effective suppression of non-radiative recombination paths, making the perovskite films more emissive.

Figure S5. SEM images of the FACs perovskite film and the BAI(top)/FACs film.

The thickness of the BAI is around 15 - 20 nm when deposited on a smooth glass substrate, which was measured by profiler. Figure S5 shows that several tens of nanometres of BAI films deposited on a rough perovskite surface, and the resulting BAI film should be discontinuous or thin enough for charge transport.

Figure S6. Tracking of maximum power point, J_{max} , and V_{max} as a function of time.

Figure S7. Thermal stability test of the perovskite films, FACS, EA-FACS, and BA-FACS kept at the temperature of 85 °C in N₂-filled glove box.

Figure S8. Long-term stability tests of the encapsulated perovskite devices by tracking MPPs under 1 Sun illumination measured in air at RH of 40% - 70%.

Figure S9. XRD profiles of the FACS and EA10%-FACS perovskite films with and without BAI-overcoated layer: (a, c) the full scan range to 50° and (b, d) a magnified scan to 17° .

To verify how the over-coated BAI incorporates with the 3D perovskite layer, we measured XRD and PL of the BAI-coated on top of FACS and EA10%-FACS perovskite (Fig. S9). The XRD profiles of BAI(top)/FACS show that the low n phase forms regardless of the heat treatment. The diffraction peak located at 4.5° indicates (020) plane coming from $n = 2$ perovskite. This is noted differently from the peak from the pristine BAI molecule whose diffraction peak located at 5.8° . The EA10%-FACS perovskite also exhibits a formation of $n = 2$ perovskite when it is coated with BAI layer. These results suggest that BAI could incorporate into perovskite layer to form low- n perovskite phase due to the favorable ion exchanging property of halide perovskite. This property enables the BAI cation to integrate with lead iodide to form low- n phase.

Figure S10. Comparison of the emission spectra of the FACs and EA10%-FACs perovskite films with and without top BAI layer, illuminated from the front (black) and glass (red) sides of the film.

To elucidate a vertical distribution of low n perovskite phase in the case of BAI-coated perovskite, we measured PL spectra by varying the illumination direction between film side and glass side (Fig. S10). The PL spectra show these low n phase mostly exists at the air-surface of perovskite in the both cases, which can be supported by that the PL emission from low n perovskite is only visible from the film side, not from the glass side.